

Working Backwards to Combat Health Misinformation

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Abstract—In the summer of 2023, a multi-disciplinary and multi-institution group of researchers joined with Amazon AWS to start a process of creating open-source templates of cloud resources to tackle health misinformation. We explain the Amazon process of ‘Working Backwards’ and how we envision cloud resources can help support future public health solutions to health misinformation online.

Index Terms—health misinformation, cloud computing, open-source, artificial intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

Around the world, physicians and health practitioners have been overwhelmed by online misinformation [1]. Much of this information ends up in the hands of patients and complicates the diagnosis and treatment of problems patients face. Delays in and resistance to sound diagnosis and treatment may lead to excess time and financial costs for practitioners and insurance companies, and impact a patient’s health and recovery, and in some extreme cases, cost the patient their life. We have been on a journey to provide an open-source health misinformation toolkit that provides a programmatic interface, relevant data, and templates to enable individuals and organizations to identify and track unverified content and rumors around diseases and treatments at scale. Although we are still in the initial phases of building out these science gateway tools, we would like to share our most unique aspect of this journey. This journey has been unique because it has truly been an effort as academic researchers to learn from industry experts when it comes to building out technology products. Our partner in this journey has been Amazon AWS and we have been using the same process to create this health misinformation toolkit

as they have used to create their own products. This process is called “Working Backwards”.

II. THE AMAZON WORKING BACKWARDS PROCESS

A. Defining the Process

Engagements following the ‘Working Backwards’ model assist teams in establishing a novel product, service, or experience, subsequently enabling a swift realization and market introduction of that solution. This concentrated and jointly intensive collaboration borrows inspiration from the customer-focused strategies employed by Amazon to create innovative breakthroughs adored by our customers, including services like Amazon Prime, Amazon Kindle, Amazon Web Services, Amazon Echo and Alexa, and Amazon Go.

B. Explaining the Process

The process begins by pinpointing a final consumer and their unique issue or prospect. Then, adhering to the ‘Working Backwards’ strategy, Amazon assists groups in devising a fresh solution that caters to the customer’s most urgent requirement. Collectively, groups actualize the concept in a forthcoming Press Release and Frequently Asked Questions document (PR-FAQ), and construct prototypes as necessary to further authenticate and refine the idea. Once a group is prepared, they leverage the AWS platform to escalate the solution.

For more extensive innovation agendas, Amazon provides a multi-stream engagement. Initially, Amazon collaborates with the group’s executive team to reach a consensus on a comprehensive vision and strategy for innovation, followed by its activation through multiple innovation work streams - each targeting a specific consumer issue or opportunity.

Whether it's about solving a single customer problem or exploring a wider opportunity landscape, 'Working Backwards' engagements allow teams to firsthand experience Amazon's approach to innovation and apply it to develop new solutions that charm your customers.

III. PROJECT HEAL

This gathering of researchers and Amazon AWS members was driven by a number of papers, presentations, and projects, which include [2], [3], [4], and [5]. The goal of this meeting was to begin a process of defining how cloud technology tools and templates can help to support the building of public health infrastructure to combat health misinformation (codename Project Heal). Brooks et al. describe extensively how the Pan American Health Organization (a sub-region of the World Health Organization) could benefit from health misinformation infrastructure [1], but the problem is that trying to build that infrastructure and tool sets from scratch is just too high of a barrier to cross within academia. To speed this building process up, cloud technology could be used to form the foundation for health misinformation resources that could be used by smaller local public health organizations.

Prior to the meeting, researchers gave feedback to an aspirational press release (part of the working backwards process). Part of the press release described a health misinformation toolkit (HMT) by stating that it, "is a direct response to the needs of those dealing with health misinformation, namely health systems and their professionals. The HMT is unique in its ability to aggregate rumors and health content from social media into proper disease categories, generate insights, can support multiple languages, and is supported by AWS's cloud-based templates, which enable people to provision all of the toolkit's benefits into their own technology environments and stacks." The goal of this project is to provide an open-source set of templates and tools that anyone can use to build out their contextualized anti-health misinformation solutions.

A. Example Artifacts of Project Heal: Customer Persona

One of artifacts that came from the working backwards process for Project Heal was defining our "customer" that would be consuming information and tools from the project. We call this customer Mary, who is a fictitious public health administrator in the Midwest who identifies as a female and is sixty years of age. We pulled an image of her from pixabay (free to use license) and outlined her education, the languages that she speaks, and information about her family and her hobbies. The reason why we did this was to try to get as close to the realm of understand our customer's needs as possible. See Figure 1.

As a note, we actually modeled Mary against a real world public health administrator, but changed major identifying characteristics of this individual. Additionally, when we tested this idea across various public health workers, we had a diverse set of individuals to receive feedback from. More information on this can be found in the "Prototyping the Idea and Gaining Feedback" section.

B. Customer Storyboard

Another artifact was a visual cartoon representation of a theoretical public health administrator's experience in using tools that would be derived from the health misinformation toolkit. We found that the ability to picture our stakeholder's engagement with what were trying to build gave us tremendously feedback in testing and refining our direction towards the actual build. We actually showed this cartoon to our public health administrators during the feedback collection process and they confirmed that this was a good representation of what they go through when it comes to health misinformation. See Figure 2.

C. Prototyping the Idea and Gaining Feedback

Through the Working Backwards process, we had two paths of work happening concurrently. The first path of work was to go through a human-centered design process in which we created enough of a visual user interface to the system that it could function as a means to gain feedback from real-world public health administrators. An example of our visual user interface that was constructed can be found in Figure 3. We conducted one hour feedback sessions with public health administrators across the United States as well as one from that larger Pan American region and all individuals confirmed the usefulness of our concept and numerous people asked if they could have the system "right now".

The second path of work was to create an initial vision for the cloud architecture, which can be found in Figure 4. Most of this architecture could be built up within days and weeks versus years.

IV. CONCLUSION

The next steps of Project Heal is to work with teams at Amazon AWS to rapidly prototype a Sprint 0 version of the technology so as to provide a minimum viable product (or minimum love-able product according to Amazon) for developers to build on top of and/or funding agencies to review. We want to provide a flexible and open back-end technology infrastructure for developers to build various front-end systems on top of so that they can build their own health misinformation dashboards that are contextualized to their needs. All of the technical architecture diagram and relevant UI mockup material will be published as open source to GitHub under the MIT license on a University of California Davis Health Cloud Innovation Center owned GitHub account [6].

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FIGURES

Customer Persona

Identifying as female
60 years old

Name: Mary Johnson
Profession: Elected Public Health Administrator
Geographic Location: Mid-Size City, IL
Education: BS, MS, MPH
Language: English Primary, Spanish Secondary
Other: Married, loves to hike, shop at local businesses, and enjoys gardening

Fig. 1. Fictitious Customer Persona

Scene 1: Mary Johnson is at a community meeting. A man asks, "WHAT'S GOING ON WITH STOMACH VIRUS X?" Another man asks, "GUY, YOU TOLD US THIS WOULD HELP!" A woman says, "...PARENTS ARE TREATING THEIR KIDS WITH BLEACH!"

Scene 2: Mary is at her desk at 4:15 pm. A colleague asks, "HAVE YOU HEARD ABOUT THIS?" Another colleague says, "IT'S ALL OVER NEWSFOUR MOM!"

Scene 3: The next morning, a colleague tells Mary about Project Heal. The screen shows "PROJECT HEAL TOP PUBLIC HEALTH THREATS IN THE US" and "EMERGING THREATS".

Scene 4: Mary is looking at a Project Heal webpage titled "STOMACH VIRUS X". The page includes sections for "YOUR HEADLINE", "PUBLIC HEALTH IMPACT", "WHAT WE KNOW", and "TOP MYTHS".

Scene 5: Mary is looking at a detailed Project Heal webpage with sections for "EVIDENCE", "HOW TO PREPARE THIS MYTH", "HOW TO DEBUNK THIS MYTH", "GENERAL RESPONSE STRATEGIES", and "INTERNAL MEMO".

Scene 6: Mary is looking at a "HEALTH ACTION PLAN FOR STOMACH VIRUS X" which includes an "INTERNAL MEMO" and a "PUBLIC STATEMENT FOR REPRESENTATION BY COMMUNICATION TEAM".

Scene 7: Six months later, Mary is presenting a "HEALTH ACTION PLAN FOR STOMACH VIRUS Z" to a group. A colleague asks, "ANY QUESTIONS?" and another says, "WOW, WE REALLY GOT AHEAD OF THIS ONE!".

Scene 8: Mary is at a community meeting. A man says, "I'VE BEEN HEARING THAT KIDS SHOULD DRINK MOTHER MILK." Another man says, "I HEARD THAT A MYTH IN GONNA CALL DE FARRER." A woman says, "I'M SO GLAD WE CAN HANG OUT IN THE EVENING NOW!"

Fig. 2. Customer Storyboard

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Search for a mis/disinformation threat to view on this map

Health community reported mis/disinformation hot spots

🕒 Top Threats
📁 Top Threat Topics
📈 Top Emerging Threats

How we get this data

24 48 72 96 126 Number of occurrences from community submissions in the last week.

152 results Filter to your district

DISEASES

You can only get Mpox through sex. [Details](#)

VACCINES

COVID-19 vaccines were used to implant microchips in people. [Details](#)

VACCINES

Only gay men can get Mpox. [Details](#)

VACCINES

Condensation trails left by planes are actually 'chemtrails' sprayed for nefarious purposes. [Details](#)

VACCINES

Vaping is harmless. [Details](#)

Report a threat!

Become a public health misinformation Ambassador in 3 quick steps.

[Go to Step 1 →](#)

[Learn more about contributing.](#)

RECENTLY VIEWED THREATS

VACCINES

The Mpox vaccine is new and unresearched.

TREATMENTS

Drinking bleach protects against COVID-19.

TREATMENTS | DRUGS

Fentanyl and Xylazine are resistant to the overdose drug Naloxone.

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Fig. 3. Example Hotspots View of Project Heal System

Fig. 4. Example Cloud Architecture of Project Heal System